

Vol:1, Issue: 3 pp: 111-120

JEL Codes: M00, M1, M10

RAZZAQ A., SARMA M., UMBREEN F. (2020). "Financial Indicators in Managerial Decision-Making",
Vol: 1 Issue: 3 pp: 111-120

Keywords: *Liquidity, working capital, liquidity management.*

Article Type Research Article

Financial Indicators in Managerial Decision-Making

Arrived Date
26.06.2020

Accepted Date
08.07.2020

Published Date
31.07.2020

Allena Razzaq*, Muhammad Sarmad†, Fariha Umbreen‡

ABSTRACT

Working capital is a financial metric which represent operating liquidity available to a business, organizational or other entity including governmental entities. Along with fix assets such as plant and equipment, working capital is considered a part of operating capital. Collaborator gets the information in working capital because of important changes. Liquidity management is one of the essential features of working capital to keep up ability of a company to pay frequently in short-term. Decision makers needed to indicators and correlations that can keep efficiently determining the real situation and identify the problems of funding in time. It is very complex task to achieving this goal because the use of various indicators and perspectives are essential to measure liquidity. For this, management and structure of organization developed by companies that provide framework to measure the liquidity. To facilitate this, the study draws attention to correlation that anticipates the actual liquidity position of a company more exactly. The database which created and identified of the annual financial statement reporting responsibility that was introduced by the Act in 2000 can be used to analyze company data on a yearly basis. Changes in indicators will be examined frequently during financial year. We need monthly or quarterly data and the addition of a suitable accounting information system for the managers to frequently get those created data that are essential for decision making and to receive information about the accomplishment of their department. The aim of study is to show the difference between the emanations of company liquidity results using only year-end data and when liquidity indicators are being accommodated a monthly basis.

INTRODUCTION

(Katrina zager, 2006) Said in his study that the decision-making process requires information financial or non-financial information as well as. The basic financial information comes from accounting which required in business activities. So, we can say the accounting is a backbone for decision-making in business actions. It essentially the procedure of collection and studies "primary data" and apply it for accessible data to take decision for business activities. The basic financial reports which accounting use to know the business worth and take decision for future

- Financial statements
- Operating statements
- Net worth

* Master of Business Administration Department, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad Sub-Campus Burewala-Vehari /PAKISTAN

† Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Technology, Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan Punjab/ PAKISTAN

‡ Okara/ PAKISTAN

*Corresponding Author Email: aleenamba786@gmail.com

- Resources

Fenyves Veronika said that working capital is necessary to fix the current financial worth of the existing company. Working capital briefly explains to better understand the business cycle of the existing company. Liquidity Management is a basic element of capital management that maintains a company's ability to give continuously

(Inta Kotane, 2012) Said in her study the significant of information about financial indicators of business activities is the financial reports of the company. The basic purpose of financial report is valuation the performance of company's business actions and financial position. Examination and evaluation of the company's business activities through economic hand, and desired solution of managerial problems may approach by the single financial indicators assessment system in the firm of compound investigation of business production. The examination of financial index, to acquire further information of financial position of a company may helpful in decision-making process.

The purpose of this study is to investigate hoe financial indicators helpful for management to take decision. Financial accounting helps the business to follow up the financial actions. The process of recording and reporting of all financial data of the business. The basic three areas where accounting helps in decision making; give basic guideline to the investors about securities and operations of the company. Creditors help about liquidity and worth of the business. It helps the managerial decision making about resources.

An appropriate capital structure is an important decision for any business organization. The decision is important not only because of the need to maximize returns of the investor and owner equity. We find that financing decisions have no significant impact on firm performance. When financing decision measured through liquidity ratio and firm's performance measured through financial indicators.

Problem Statement

The main purpose of any is making return on investment. It this statement we see the behaviour of financial position of these firm, the statement is an achieve from which the necessary information as to whether a system, decision, technique, etc. Is effective or not. These statements provide the past decision and techniques with regards to their effectiveness and therefore informed a fact-based decision on the side of management as to the degree of control needed in a system. The validity of investment or a decision enhances their ascertainment of the goal of organization.

Research Objectives

- ✚ To identify the financial position of sugar mill
- ✚ To identify the past decision making on investment weather it's favourable or not
- ✚ To identifying the new factors of decision on investment that firm can make new investment or not.

Significant of Study

The main objective of study is identifying the better utilization of resources. Problems and challenges that are facing by these firms. Quick and correct decision-making result for business growth. Rational decision helps to the organization to achieve its objectives. It is helpful for increasing the efficiency and facilitate to innovation in firm.

LITERATURE REVIEW

(AKMAL KHAN, 2017)Described the capital structure choices are necessary for any concern. The choices is very important owing to the necessity to maximize returns to numerous structure constituencies associated additionally owing to the impact such a call has on an organization's ability to agitate with its competitive atmosphere. The key's for corporations to settle on a portfolio of capital structure which will maintain property and generate a lot of wealth.

One of necessary assumptions in higher cognitive process and improvement economy is existence of quality information. Vital variety of this information comes from accounting information systems and from monetary statements. Monetary statements must be compelled to give realistic and objective image of realistic business condition of bound company. In alternative words, auditing of economic statements is intelligible, by that accuracy is ensured. In context of thoughts of economic statements as a operate of higher cognitive process it's necessary to stress that completely different users should shrewdness to "read" those statements. "Reading" contents of economic statements give integer of various instruments and analyses procedures for understanding business. A well-established method of management on the idea of the monetary statements and monetary information is one amongst foremost vital presumptions of the standard business.

J.B Maverick describe the main advantage of equity financing is that there's no obligation to repay the cash no heritable through it. Of course, a company's home owners need it to achieve success and supply equity investors an honest come back on their investment, however while not needed payments or interest charges as is that the case with debt financing.

The Equity finance places no extra monetary burden on the corporate. Since there are not any needed monthly payments related to equity finance, the corporate has additional capital offered for invest to growing the business. However, that does not mean there isn't any drawback to equity finance. In fact, the drawback is kind of giant. To achieve funding, you'll get to provide the capitalist a proportion of your company. You'll get to share your profits and seek advice from your new partners any time you create choices moving the corporate. The sole thanks to take away investors is to shop for buy them out, however which will doubtless be dearer than the cash they originally gave you.

J.B Maverick said in his study the debt finance typically comes with restrictions on the company's activities which will forestall it from taking advantage of opportunities outside the realm of its core business creditor's look favourably upon a comparatively low debt-to-equity quantitative relation. That edges the corporate if it must access extra debt finance within the future.

The advantages of debt finance area unit various. First, the investor has no management over your business. Once you pay the loan back, your relationship with the financier ends. Next, the interest you pay is tax deductible. Finally, it's simple to forecast expenses as a result of because loan payments don't fluctuate.

(Clark, 1993) Myrtle W. Clark recently discusses on distinctive between liability and equity instruments address the difficulty of whether to continue the sharp distinction between debt and equity. Paton's entity theory is cited as a potential basis for rewarding the record as asset=equities. Consistent with this theory, subbing one kind of capital for an additional doesn't influence operations, because of debt and equity supplier's area unit nearly are indistinguishable. A review of the money social science provides a basis for final that alternative to equity finance influence future money flows. Hence, the excellence between debt and equity ought to continue. Moreover, preferred shares and money possibility contracts influence firm worth otherwise from common equity. Support is found for viewing each as liabilities. Finally, because of individual elementary money instruments have information content, the elements of compound money instruments ought to be disclosed.

(Marsh, 1982). Paul Marsh targeted on empirical study of security issues by Britain firms between 1959 and 1974 focuses on however firms choose between financing instruments at a given purpose in time. It throws light on variety of attention-grabbing queries. First, it demonstrates that firm's area unit heavily influenced by market conditions and the history of security cost in selecting between debt and equity. Second, it provides proof that firms seem to create their alternative of finance instrument as if they need target levels of debt in mind. Finally, the results area unit according to the notion that these target debt levels area unit themselves a perform of company size, bankruptcy risk, and quality composition

(Czarnitzki & Kraft, 2009) Focused on debt finance reduces the variations between weak and powerfully controlled managers. Debt works as a robust commitment to lift the returns necessary to hide the interest payments. Therefore, it reduces the probabilities of managers to pursue alternatives

aims than profit maximization. Hence, potential variations because of the degree of management through the house owners ought to scale back or disappear with increasing leverage. The debt level disciplines the management. Hence, debt interacted with weak internal control reduces the discretionary power of the managers, in order that variations because of possession (if present) area unit reduced through management by the credit market.

(Kono, 2010) Introduced the balanced budget significant financial performance as one of the key indicators of firm's success and helped decision making process. To attenuate the firm's value of capital by dominant the capital structure (debt magnitude relation or leverage).

Firm's set economic added goals to effectively confirm their business worth and improve the resources allocation. Companies must deal with indicators to grasp the firm's position, and use internal sources utilize their own resources on the market. Today companies work with ever longer payment periods that mean credits terms conjointly longer than before. Money statements facilitate to call the decision makers to require decision by giving information supported on assets or financial gain.

(Scott) Said in his study the one way is to know the business health using key performance indicators. Current ratio gives you with a measure of liquidity. Key performance indicators to work out if you have got the mandatory money accessible to fund an oversized purchase. Current quality's square measure things like money or asset that you simply expect to right way convert into money among a year. Current liabilities square measure debts that you simply to repay during a year. The short quantitative relation is another indicator to work out the business health. The short quantitative relation is best do than a current quantitative relation to understand concerning short-run monetary business activities. If you're attempting to form strategic deciding for your company, you need to use key performance indicators. These indicators assist you to higher perceive your company's health.

(Jasmina Bagicevic, 2016) Said in her study the accounting plays an important role in evaluating the business performance through the financial statements. To check the beginning hypothesis, qualitative methodology is going to be used, supported the study and a descriptive analysis of the analysis drawback, while, supported empirical studies by varied authors within the field of accounting and business political economy and management, the aggregation of various positions is going to be dispensed, through the strategy of synthesis and deduction. On the total, no matter whether monetary efficiency is treated within the slim or broad sense, the most sources used for its analysis are unit provided by data within the statement of monetary standing, earning reports, and web price. In fact, even the authors WHO advocate a narrower conception of monetary situation take information from each profit-and-loss statement and statement of monetary stand for the assessment of worldwide profitability indicators.

(Notes) said in his article the organizations operate by corporal punishment choices. A manager plans, organizes, staffs, leads, and controls her team by accomplish decisions. The fitness and standard of these choices confirm however winning a manager. The decision-making method begins once a manager identifies the important downside. The correct definition of the matter affects all the steps that follow; if the matter is inaccurately outlined, each step within the decision-making method are supported associate incorrect starting line. A way that a manager will facilitate determines truth downside in a very scenario is by characteristic the matter individually from its symptoms. Time pressures often cause a manager to manoeuvre forward once considering solely the primary or most blatant answers. However, winning downside determination needs thorough examination of the challenge, and a fast answer might not lead to a permanent answer. Thus, a manager ought to assume through and investigate many various solutions to one downside before creating a fast call.

(S*, 2016) Focused on the basic objective of the firms to maximize its profits and in the same time minimize its cost. Capital structure was outlined first by Modigliani and Miller because the combine between debt and equity that the uses in its operation. Since Modigliani and Miller's theory has been printed several of the researchers are still learning the link between capital structure and firm performance, some of them found that there is a negative relation between capital structure and firm performance, whereas others found a positive relation between capital structure and firm performance. In another hand several papers said a big to a relation between structure and firm

performance, whereas several of them said associate degree insignificant relation between structure and firm performance.

(Vesic, 2017) Said in her study the monetary reports offer the essential information for business deciding. Management of the corporate continually centered on the perception of future events as a results of gift call. The monetary analysis effects the business deciding. Management choices that assess the monetary the monetary statements, that square measure the set of economic records that a corporation should processed all business call that was created by management. The method of study is testing and evaluating in terms of methodology, that is coloured and run across, supported the assumption: that the assessment is that the completion of the analysis, that is preceded by testing methodology developed that provides a basis of the part that square measure combined into one synthesis of a logical statement. The scientific work points to the role and significance of the results provided by the monetary analysis for business call.

(Ponikvar, 2009) Investigated in her analysis the impact of growth on monetary and nonfinancial indicators and additionally as well as accounting for imperceptible individual effects of every firm. Authors showed that the knowing the impact of growth rates on monetary ratios offers managers abundant information for creating business deciding. Current ratios indicate however expeditiously a firm applies on assets. A Liquidity quantitative relation offers information a couple of firm's abilities to fulfil its monetary obligations. This analysis includes two of the foremost often used liquidity quantitative relations: current ratio, a quantitative relation of current assets and current liabilities, and fast quantitative relation, a quantitative relation of the distinction between current assets and inventory to current liabilities. The results of the analysis indicate that gain, liquidity, "current assets" value, value of capital, and productivity square measure associated with firm growth. The managers realize some ratios and utilized in business deciding. Therefore, managers ought to take into thought the characteristics of their trade and their competitors once creating business choices associated with these ratios and measures.

(Avakmovic, 2016) Aforementioned in her study, within the past if we've got booming in creating choices. It's a decent indicator of future success. typically, investors or individual appearance at the course of previous sales, expenses, net income, money flows and therefore the movement of financial gain, not solely as a company's success, however additionally as potential indicators of future success. The symptoms are wont to measure the firm's potency. Comparison of indicators and management activities is worthy in terms of economic management of the enterprise, as a relation and effects of the investment directly verify the extent of liquidity and gain of the business. The techniques and strategies want to verify the economic condition and performance of the participating the monetary ratios.

(Julius) focused on the study of economic indicators that utilized in business deciding. In each business, there square measure wants for information. This information used in production, financial, promoting etc. usually the larger firm's want lot of information. Monetary report plays a very important role in deciding process of business organizations. Most of the managers nowadays, rush into fast deciding while not correct analysis of the result of such choices on the value and gain. In different words, a course of actions in any organization is perennial solely to live its fastened goals. The monetary statements square measure records from that the vital information is employed for deciding or for techniques. These statements provide managements the required model for the examination and analysis of the past choices and techniques with regards to the effectiveness of the business.

E.A. Osadchy delineated the aim of the study to boost the construct of getting ready the monetary statements of a corporation as information to require call for business. Today, the monetary statements square measure the foremost complete, objective and correct information base for the corporate. Coverage is employed by company's management because basis for creating social control choices. This information is vital for the analysis of organization's activities. The system of indicators that represents the monetary statements ought to be output directly from the ledger accounts- the

most important register of the accounting system. Supported the system of indicators of monetary coverage for users to research the financial position of the firm.

Research Design

The process of testing and assessment in the analysis of a business has its own specific test methods that are based on theoretical and scientific shame. Financial analysis is used to assess relationship between items within the financial statements. This scientific work points to the role and significance of the results provided by financial analysis for business decision making.

Population

A population refers to a group individuals or things with similar characteristics that an enquiry intends to review and to draw applied math inferences or conclusions. The population of the study is formed up to the five corporations of sugar business in Asian country.

Data Collection

This study used secondary information that was obtained from the annual audited money statements that had audited and revealed by the sugar business firms listed at exchange in Islamic Republic of Pakistan. The annual revealed money reports were obtained from the foremost recent years for a amount of five years between 2014 and 2018. Cash Ratio, Current Ratio and Quick Ratio are used to analyse the financial statement of different sugar mills (Shahtaj Sugar mill, Fatima Sugar Mill, Chesham Sugar Mill, JWD Sugar mill and Al-Noor Sugar Mill) to the financial position of the company. Secondary data are collected from these companies of last five years (2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, and 2018). After collecting data, excel sheet are used to measuring the data. The output result shown on graph which shows the financial positions of given companies of last five years.

Research Hypothesis

Decision taken by relationship between ratios as dependent variable and liquidity ratios as the independent variables are derived. In this study, financial indicators (cash ratio, current ratio, quick ratio) considered as an independent variable, and decision making is considered as a dependent variable.

H0: Negative effect of financial indicators on managerial decision making.

H1: Positive effect of financial indicators on managerial decision making.

FINDINGS

Figure 1

The chart shows the data of Al- NOOR Sugar Mill. In which cash and current ratios are same of all years but quick was increase in 2014 and after it decrease.

We have used the annual data that allowed us to compare yearly results. Data shows the company does not have the liquidity problems in current year and company face the quick ratio in 2014. When analysing the yearly data the bigger fluctuations can be seen.

Figure 2

The chart shows the data of Chashma Sugar Mill. In which cash and current ratios are same of all years but quick was increase in 2014 and after it decrease. We can also see the yearly general liquidity ratio to be volatile in 2014. After looking at figure 3-2 we can draw the conclusion that yearly general data shows a lot more accurate and realistic picture about the liquidity position of the company. The liquidity ratios were different in the end of the studied years: in 2014 the quick ratio is higher, while in 2015 the three ratios were nearly the same in the end of the year. A company is more liquid in the periods it has a lot of cash and marketable securities than in the periods of big inventories. That's the reason why general liquidity ratio is not a reliable indicator to show a company's ability to pay. Quick ratio of a company can be seen on figure 2.

Figure 3

The chart shows the data of Fatima Sugar Mill. In which cash and current and quick ratios are same of all years and quick ratio increase in 2018.

The quick ratio ignores the most illiquid assets of a company, but the analysed one had significant amount of cash, which has caused differences between the values of the general liquidity ratios and quick ratio. The quick ratio is increased in current year and the cash ratio and current ratio is nearly same in yearly data.

Figure 4

The chart shows the data of JWD Sugar Mill. In which cash and current ratios are same of all years but quick was rapidly increase in with the passage year.

The significance of the yearly values in evaluation is evidenced in these results too. Looking at the yearly data we can also draw a conclusion that the values of the ratios are fluctuating in greater or lesser extent. When the quick ratio is temporarily higher above the accepted range.

Figure 5

The chart shows the data of Shahtaj Sugar Mill. In which cash and current ratios are same of all years but quick ratio continuously changes.

In case of yearly cash ratios there is a different tendency as the previous ratio, the values of the indicators were higher. Which indicates the very bad liquidity situation. In yearly data we can see the fluctuation in quick ratio. In 2014 the current ratio was increased by the amount of 2.5 lac and quick ratio was increased by 5 lac and cash ratio was constant in that year. The quick liquidity ratio was higher in 2017 at the peak.

INTERPRETATION OF FINDING

The findings show that financial indicators have a positive effect on managerial decision making because results show that when companies use the current ratio, quick ratio, and cash ratio, then profitability will be increased by effecting decision making through financial indicators. In short, the finding shows that financial indicators are helpful for increasing earnings by effective decision making.

Hypothesis 1

Financial indicators have a positive effect on managerial decision making.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using different liquidity indicators, we try to anticipate whether companies can meet their short-term liabilities using their available current assets. Liquidity ratios have a great benefit of being relatively accurate regarding their components because on the short-term, there are more realistic data available in the accounting system than for analysing long-term assets and sources. However, we must keep in mind that liquid asset prices change fast, that's why these indicators can become outdated in a short period of time. Therefore, when we implement liquidity tests, a continuous monitoring is necessary. In case of certain fields of activity, the degree of liquidity can differ seasonally. Nowadays, it is very important for the management to receive new information the fastest possible, because this is the only way to act quickly. The earlier an effect can be seen – whether it is negative or positive –, the sooner it can be managed or taken advantage of. This is the exact reason why the continuous observation of the company's operations and data analysing is essential for companies. One of the sources of data to be used for the analysis could be the annual report for those companies that are legally bound to prepare it. Annual reports of the companies are required by the Act C of 2000 which has been amended several times since its implementation. However, to keep track of the changes in these indicators during the year, (monthly and/or quarterly) data is needed. For the managers to receive the necessary and essential information for decision-making, the adaptation of an adequate accounting information system is required, moreover, to get feedback about the performance of their department.

Conclusion

We can draw the conclusion that yearly collected data shows a lot of more accurate and realistic picture about the financial position of the company. It is important to continuously monitor liquidity ratios that help determine a company's financial position, but for this, monthly or quarterly closing of the books is required. This is not only important because of the monitoring, but also the timely decision making. For the management, nowadays it is not enough to focus on the decision, but the time factor is getting more and more important. Another factor is the follow-up of the decisions' results in case of successful companies. Monthly closings could help to make these observations, and operating results can be analysed in detail, too. Companies, their creditors and internal stakeholders should be aware of the liquidity and solvency situation of a given company, which can be measured by different liquidity ratios. However, traditional liquidity ratios do not sufficiently consider how long their components are tied for the operation of the company, which significantly affects their values. Adjusted liquidity ratios can be used to solve this problem.

Limitation

There is limitation in this research that there are few ratios used (Cash Ratio, Quick ratio & Current ratio) this study to analyse the financial position of industries. These ratios are not enough to analyse the financial statement of huge firm. The time is also limited for this research. There should be huge study with more variable and ratio for measuring the data to seeing the financial positions.

REFERENCE

- Akmal K., M. S. (2017). Impact of Financing Decision on Firm's Performance; an Empirical Study Ofpakistani Listed Firm's In Kse.
- Avakmovic, J, J. A. (2016). Methods of Financial Analysis and Impact on Quality of Decision Making.
- Bagicevic, J. V. D. (2016). The Role Financial and Non-Financial Performance Indicators in Enterprize Sustainability Evaluation.
- Clark, M. W. (1993). Entity Theory, Modern Capital Structure Theory, and the Distinction between Debt and Equity.
- Czarnitzki, D., & Kraft, K. (2009). Capital Control, Debt Financing and Innovative Activity. *Journal of Econonmic Behavior & Organization*, 32.
- Julius, S. (N.D.). The Impact of Financial Statement on the Managerial Decision Making Of Mattel Europa B.V, Netherland.
- Kotane, I. K.-M. (2012). Assessment of Financial Indicators for Evaluation of Business Performance.
- Marsh, P. (1982). The Choice between Equity and Debt: An Empirical Study.
- Pedro, M.Kono, D. A. (2010). The Role of Finance in the Strategic-Planning and Decision Making Process.
- Ponikvar, N. M. T. (2009). Performance Ratios for Managerial Decision-Making in a Growing Firm. Notes, C. (N.D.). The Decision Making Process.
- S*, N. (2016). The Impact of Capital Structure on Financial Performanceof the Firms: Evidence from Borsa Istanbul. *Journal Ofbusiness & Financial Affairs*.
- Scott, C. (N.D.). Eight Financial Kpi's to Help Your Business's Performances.
- Vesic, T., S. A. (2017). The Importance of Financial Analysis for Business Decision Making.
- Zager, K. L. Z. (2006). The Role of Financial Informatiom in Decision Making Process. *Innovative Marketing*, 7.